

ANEX I

Abstract Submission

After reading carefully the guidelines please submit your abstract in the system, as by guidelines in the webpage.

Here you can find the details for all types of submissions and how to submit your abstract.

The authors shall please check the guidelines below and the information in the Call for Abstracts, and read our Publication Ethics and Malpractice Statement.

TYPES OF SUBMISSIONS

Posters (Virtual Presentations)

This submission type is an alternative format for freestanding research presenters. Poster sessions offer an informal yet personalized format for the dissemination and exchange of information.

A poster/demonstration must:

- Contain implemented information work about a subject;
- Be informative but also engaged visually and easy to understand.

Initially, this submission type must include an abstract. Keep in mind that if your abstract gets selected for publication, you will be asked for a final complete paper (limited to 3-5 pages long), besides the poster/demonstration itself.

- Accomplished empirical or theoretical research with corresponding results or reports;

- or New developments in the given themes, employing qualitative or quantitative methods of either primary or secondary data.

This submission type gives the opportunity for those who cannot be at the conference meeting physically, but wish to participate, showcasing their work through different media.

The conference will provide a link with virtual content that will be sent by email to all participants. All the Poster Presentation files will be uploaded by us onto a webpage with the respective details so that all the conference participants can have access to them during and after the conference. This submission type can include:

Poster Virtual Presenters must also be registered for the conference, their papers are considered to be published as the others and are also entitled to the certificate of participation in the conference. Initially, this submission type must include an abstract.

ANEX II

HOW TO SUBMIT ONLINE

Abstracts must be submitted through our step-by-step Electronic Submission System. We do not accept the submission of Abstracts by email.

Step 1 - Author(s) Information

Fill the “Author Information” box by order of representation.

The information of each author must be complete, these are the contacts that will be used to communicate with the authors.

IMPORTANT NOTES:

- In the initial submission phase, we only accept abstracts, not complete papers or posters.
- This is the ONLY place where you give your personal details – the Abstract file must be ANONYMOUS (i.e. remove name, institution, address, as well as any acknowledgments that may lead to information about the authors).
- Please DO NOT use any Accent marks and/or Diacritical marks in the submission form, since our online platform doesn't recognize them.
- This conference has defined a maximum limit of 4 submissions per author (including co-authored proposals), but please note that one author registration only covers a maximum of 2 accepted presentations (Poster). Submissions beyond this limit will not be considered.

Step 2 - Paper Information

Type your abstract/paper title in the first box and in “Paper Abstract” box, paste your main text from your abstract paper file – this will guarantee the association of your contact details with your

abstract, while the abstract file maintains anonymity for the refereeing procedure.

Then, upload your file in doc, rtf or PDF formats only - no other formats will be accepted (like .ppt files, for example).

The file max. size is 5 Mb.

In the “Track” boxes select the topic areas you are submitting to:

- Select one of the 5 main areas
- Select the sub-theme(s) corresponding to that main area.
- Finally select the “Presentation Type”: Poster

Final Step - Make sure the mandatory fields are covered and then click the SUBMIT button.

Once you have submitted your abstract, you will receive an email confirming receipt (check your SPAM folder, just in case). If you don't receive an email after 24 hours, please contact the conference secretariat at

scientiae-naturalis-registration@yahoo.com

Please make sure that our emails are not considered SPAM.

ANEX III

Final Submission & Copyright

NOTE: ONLY for author(s) who had their abstract(s) accepted

Please follow these two steps:

1. Please download the Final Submission Template (please fill it in with your submission information, according to how is written on the template and your work, deleting the unnecessary text).

Important notes: The final submission paper should be complete and it is limited to 5 pages long for Poster Virtual Presentation papers (including abstract, keywords, and references). Send it with the below copyright form (follow the instructions given in the notification email).

Only the full text of the papers will be published in the current volume of the book "The Doha deadlock: Intellectual Property and Climate Change". The abstracts will be published in the Book of Abstracts. Please check the detailed information in the Publications section.

2. Copyright Form – Click on the thumbnail of the available formats to download:

Please fill out, sign, print, digitalize, and send it by email to: ***scientiae-naturalis-registration@yahoo.com***.

3. Send the final submission file of your paper or poster through your author corner (please use your login and password, available at the bottom of the notification email, to access it).

4. Please follow thoroughly the Norms based on APA (American Psychological Association, 2010) 6th edition of Publication Manual of the American Psychological Association, and APA style® (<http://www.apastyle.org/>) referencing guide and other minor sources

ANEX IV

Guidelines for Presenters

Here you can find the details for all types of presentations.

REQUIREMENTS / NOTES FOR PRESENTERS:

Posters

Presenters are required to prepare the content in a full-sized poster, with the following requirements:

- Dimensions: Poster size should be no more than A0 portrait (approx. 84 x 115 cm).
- We recommend that you use a heavyweight paper or thin card.
- As they can be viewed from a certain distance, please make sure your typeface and graphics are easy to read; we recommend you to use a font size for: Title: 20-24 mm or 100 points maximum/bold. Make sure your title, authors and affiliated institutions/contact details are clearly visible at the top of your presentation to give to interested delegates. Headings: 48 points suggested 60 points at max. title case headings such as Introduction, Methods, Results, Discussion and Conclusions are useful. Results can be presented in the form of graphics, avoiding large data tables, using colours, symbols, pictures, etc. Content: 20-28 point, 32 point at max (single spaced).
- Please note that the official conference language is English, French, Spanish and Arabic; all posters must be displayed in English, French, Spanish and Arabic.
- Keep the amount of text in your posters brief, focusing on a few key points. Any description of the methods should be simple and concise. The conference will include timetabled sessions providing an opportunity for presenters and participants to discuss work and findings. Presenters should be near their posters in case anyone wishes to pose questions.

Presenters should deliver the Posters duly identified at the welcome desk when making the check-in to the conference. We will display the Posters in the presentation room before the session starts. Please remember to take your poster materials with you after your presentation. Any posters remaining at the end of the conference will be discarded.

Virtual Presentations

Presenters that will not be present at the conference, but will participate with a virtual contribution, must also be registered in the conference, their papers are considered to be published as the others and are also entitled to the certificate of participation in the conference. Presenters are required to prepare the content for the presentation itself, which can be made in one of these two ways (in no particular order):

- Recording a video of the presentation,
- or, Creating a PowerPoint presentation with slides and a voice-over, and save it as a video.(the file that you send us must be in VIDEO format, we won't accept any other file formats, like .ppt files)

1) About recording a video presentation: You can record your presentation through a camcorder, web camera or mobile phone with at least 4 megapixels quality. Feel free to open your video in an editing program (Windows Movie Maker, iMovie, AVID, Final Cut Pro or other editing software), according to your expertise and convenience, to make alterations and all kinds of editing (putting a title, your name, etc). Save your file either in *.AVI, *.MPG, *.WMV, *.MP4 or *.MOV (extensions format).

2) About creating a PowerPoint presentation with a voice-over: Use the PowerPoint program or similar (available in any Operating System) to compose your presentation in slides. This software is convenient and easier for almost all people, but you're welcome to use other tools, to create advanced presentations. We suggest you start by presenting a picture of yourself with email contact or affiliations, with a welcome message to the audience, feel free to use your creativity, but try to keep it easy and brief. Use an audio recording device, such as a microphone or other external voice

recorder, music, etc. Once you have your PowerPoint slides, you can insert the audio files using the program itself – click Insert > Movies and Sounds > Sound from file (choosing the location of your audio files). You can also record your voice with PowerPoint on each slide, if desired – click Insert > Movies and Sounds > Record sound. One can create self-running slides, including voice narration. After you made the synchronized PowerPoint presentation, turn it into a movie file – click File > Make Movie – the opened window will allow you to choose the location where you want to save your video from the PowerPoint presentation (save your file either in *.AVI, *.MPG, *.WMV, *.MP4 or *.MOV (extensions format)).

Important note for videos and PowerPoint videos:

- Spoken or written words must be in English.
- Try to achieve a good quality voice recording, to facilitate the hearing, by making it in a quiet setting and by speaking clearly and in a paused manner.
- Videos and PowerPoint videos should be kept simple, transmitting information clearly, like in a poster presentation with the respective contents. Use clear and visible characters in the writings when editing text or topics.
- Review and watch various times your video and its contents in your software player.
- You **MUST NOT EXCEED** a 10 minutes' presentation and 100 MB of space file.
- The presentation file should be sent by email to scientiae-naturalis-registration@yahoo.com or

scientiae-naturalis-marketing@yahoo.com

through Dropbox, Google Drive, or WeTransfer.

The conference will provide a link with virtual content that will be sent by email to all participants. The pre-recorded Video Presentations will be available on the conference's YouTube channel. The videos will not be public, only those with access to

the links will be able to see them. The links for the videos will be available on our website, with the respective details, so that all the conference participants can have access to them during and after the conference. This will give the opportunity for presenters who cannot be at the conference meeting physically but wish to participate, to showcase their work through different media.

The authors of the Virtual Presentations can be contacted via email by any conference participant who wishes to discuss the contents of the presentation.

COPYRIGHT AGREEMENT

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scientiae-naturalis-registration@yahoo.com**

If there is more than one author, all authors must sign this form. If the authors are in different locations, each one can sign different copies of the copyright agreement and send them separately.

ANEX V

This Copyright Agreement aims to guarantee that only original material is published, giving however significant freedom to authors.

The DohaConference Copyright Agreement is very flexible, meaning that there is no copyright transfer to the publisher and the authors hold exclusive copyright to their work.

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their contents meet all the requirements, including provisions covering originality, authorship, author responsibilities and author misconduct.

Author(s) must only submit original work that hasn't appeared elsewhere for publication, nor is under review for another refereed publication.

Authors(s) must confirm whether disclosure of their material, content and photographs requires the prior consent of other parties and, if so, should obtain it.

Research carried out in collaboration with other scholars must have the approval of all authors, on submitting the contents.

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